

(figure, e). The receptive female remained quiescent, lifted her wings, and further curved her abdomen (copulatory acceptance posture) (figure, d). After the female accepted the male, the pair immediately turned 180° (figure, f), hung upside down for a second (figure, g), and landed on a substrate, assuming a posterior-to-posterior copulation orientation. Unless the pair was disturbed,

mating was quiescent; wing movement and antenna vibration ceased (figure, h).

Aside from the sex pheromones females released during calling, both sexes most likely release other olfactory and tactile stimuli for copulation to occur. Further investigations are necessary to verify these stimuli and identify their specific functions. □

Diagrammatic representation of *M. panalis* mating sequence.

Population fluctuation of leaffolder (LF) at different planting times in some rice varieties

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Rice LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* is a serious pest in Andhra Pradesh when planting extends from Jul to mid-Sep because of varied rainfall.

We studied the effect of four planting times on LF incidence in BPT2740, BPT11978, MTU6861, MTU2400, and MTU7029.

Varieties were planted in a split-plot design with three replications. No insecticide was used. Total leaves and damaged leaves were counted on 20 randomly selected hills/plot, 60 d after transplanting.

LF damage increased significantly with delayed planting date. There was no difference in damage among the varieties (see table). □

Effect of planting time on LF incidence. RRU, Bapatla, AP, India, 1986-87 kharif.

Planting time	Damaged leaves ^a (%)
15 Aug 1986	37.7
30 Aug 1986	47.8
15 Sep 1986	57.3
30 Sep 1986	64.8
Mean	
LSD	1.9

^a Values are angular transformations.

Survey of ricefield insects in Mbo and Ndop Plains of Cameroon

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Rice is mainly produced in the northern Sahelian Region of Cameroon. The rest is cultivated in the Western Highland Savanna, mainly in the Mbo and Ndop Plains, with an estimated 210 ha and 3,000 ha of irrigated rice, respectively.

During the 1987-89 survey, we collected and documented insect species